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Investigating Health and Exposure Circumstances of Persons after Aircraft Fume Events: A Narrative Review with Medical Protocol

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Abstract

This document lays out a consensus approach, by internationally recognised experts, to the recognition, investigation and management of persons suffering from the toxic effects of inhaling pyrolysed engine oil and other fluids contaminating the air conditioning systems in most aircraft. A best practice medical protocol is outlined and addresses the recommended actions and investigations to be undertaken for those suffering ill-health following FE and presenting In-flight, immediately Post-flight (within 1-2 days) and later/subsequently (beyond 2 days).

Keywords

aerotoxic syndrome, fume events, ill-health, treatment, medical protocol

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1 Introduction

Pyrolysed engine oil fumes contaminating the aircraft cabin air conditioning systems has been recognised and well documented since the 1950s. It is now clear that inhalation of these potentially toxic fumes in aircraft cabins causes ill-health. There is a clear and well documented history linking the onset of ill health with fume exposure in most cases. It is now clear that cumulative exposure to regular small exposures is also damaging and may be exacerbated by a single more concentrated exposure. Whilst organophosphates have been the main subject of interest, it is also clear that there are numerous volatile organic hydrocarbons in the aircraft air supply, which are likely, based on experience outside the aircraft industry, to contribute to this form of ill-health. Assessment is made more complex because of the limitations in looking at individual substances in complex heated mixtures.

The lack of acceptance of illness caused by exposure to pyrolysed engine oil, de-icing and hydraulic fluid in bleed air and aircraft air supplies is likely to be due to lack of knowledge and clinical acumen. The easier finding of more clinically acceptable diagnoses in unexplained clinical presentations is recognised.

This document lays out a consensus approach, by internationally recognised experts, to the recognition, investigation and management of persons suffering from the toxic effects of inhaling pyrolysed engine oil and other fluids contaminating the air conditioning systems in most aircraft. A best practice medical protocol is outlined including actions and investigations for in flight, immediately post flight and late subsequent follow up.

The then almost completed first “final draft” of the medical protocol was presented at this Conference in 2019. Since then, the authors have updated the document with comments on emerging areas of investigation and additional medical and scientific material. The aim of the presentation at the 2021 Conference is to provide an update on further progress to date to those who attended eighteen months ago and to inform those who have not been made aware of the status of this work. The authors are aware that this manuscript has taken many years to write and acknowledge that this has been because of the moving landscape – new scientific and medical information that needed to be included and the difficulty of harnessing numerous experts who were and are already have huge demands on their time. The authors also recognise that there have been a number of Guidelines putting forward recommendations for actions to be undertaken at the time of and following a FE.

The term and existence of ‘Aerotoxic Syndrome’ was coined by Winder and Balouet in 20001 to describe the constellation of symptoms experienced by persons exposed to FEs. The term has been criticized by some groups for a number of reasons. However, the authors have used here as it is the term used in the original publication¹.

2 Technical Matters

There is a medical need to recognise and understand a number of technical issues that that are raised in the context of FEs.

It is not generally understood in the medical community that the aircraft cabin is a closed environment with a high human occupancy and that outside air is being used to flush the cabin air and assist with pressurisation. In this regard it is different from a modern sealed building as air exchange rates are greater than in commercial and other modern buildings. This air enters the cabin through the engine and may be contaminated by pyrolysed engine oil leaking through oil seals except in the Boeing 747 Dreamliner which has an air supply independent of the engine.

It is also important to recognise that there are no fine lines separating those who will experience ill-health during or after a fume event and those who are not affected. The regular defence used by industry is that environmental concentrations of toxic substances are all below industry accepted standards. This defence ignores the fact that these standards are set to protect most persons exposed but not all. Furthermore, these standards are not available for all pyrolysed substances, all have been set for ground level and, thus, cannot be extrapolated to the cabin environment and take no account for altitude nor pyrolysed complex mixtures.

3 Medical Matters

The medical presentations of persons who have been exposed to FEs are variable and well-described in the literature². In summary, these initially, and consistently, involve the symptoms of foggy thinking, dizziness, recognising an odour in the cabin, (commonly described as a 'dirty socks' smell), impaired short-term memory and cognitive thinking, fatigue, headache, nausea, tremor, balance, incoordination, breathing difficulties, cough, chest pain, eye, nose and throat irritation. Many other symptoms, with a delayed onset, have also been reported, but the common factor that binds both the acute and delayed complaints is that they are all consistent with volatile organic hydrocarbon and organophosphate toxicity.

Medical management is related to the presenting symptomology at the time of examination and specific investigations will vary in each case, depending on specific technical and individual contextual factors. The duration of ill-health is very variable. Symptoms may last for hours, days, weeks or months. Sometimes full recovery never occurs. Persons with ongoing symptoms should ideally be followed-up and reviewed by experienced medical professionals. Our publication outlines ongoing management and investigation in detail.

The time of presentation of illness following a FE is important. Symptoms characteristically occur in one of several time frames being:

In-flight

Immediately post-flight (within 1-2 days)

Late/subsequent (beyond 2 days)

It is important that careful records are kept at the time of exposure to a FE as these will assist with ongoing medical management. In particular, these include:

the physical aspect of the exposure (type of aircraft, where if the aircraft, stage of flight, smells/odours etc)

a careful medical record of symptoms and signs, oxygen use, any treatment given, history of flying (log books etc).

4 Emerging Areas

A number of matters germane to the subject of FEs and Aerotoxic Syndrome have come to the authors' attention during the ongoing development of our manuscript. These include the recognition that fine particles affect health and that ultrafine (nanoparticles) are now accepted as being more toxic. Experience has shown that low level fume exposures are almost certainly occurring on a regular basis and that they almost certainly have a cumulative effect. These observations underscore the need to improve air quality standards in aircraft.

5 Medical Protocol

Since our last presentation of this manuscript in 2019 a significant amount of additional material has been added. These include additional material and expansions of the following sections:

- Neurology and neurotoxicity
- Best collection times for anticholinesterases
- Effect of anticholinesterases on different nervous systems
- Effect of recurrent and cumulative low dose exposure
- Effect of ultrafine (nanoparticles) particles
- Association with fatigue, sleep disorders, infection, malignancy, visual disturbance, arthritic symptoms
- Other possible associated conditions eg malignancy, chemical sensitivity

6 Summary

In summary, the medical protocol is now completed and in the editing phase. The authors accept that it has been a long journey but have wished to make the work the most comprehensive to date. It is a consensus document prepared by internationally recognised experts in their fields. A pocket size booklet is also being prepared for easy portability and reference at the time of a FE.

List of References

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